

MGNERGA as Development Practice in India: An Economic Analysis

DR. TRAILOKYA DEKA

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics
B.P. Chaliha College, Nagarbera, Kamrup, Assam (India)

ABSTRACT:

Presently Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is the largest Public Employment guarantee Programme in the world. Data collected through field survey in Assam (India) state and using the tools of economic analysis of PSM (Propensity Score Matching) and DiD (Difference in Difference), this article makes a evaluation of the 'Development Practice' of MGNREGA with respect to one important indicators of inclusive development i.e. creation of income and employment. The paper finds that MGNREGA has been instrumental in increasing the income and wage employment base of the rural economy. In a broader sense, the study reinforces the relevance of state sponsored development practices like MGNREGA in expanding the capability vector of individuals and communities in the process of economic development.

Keywords: MGNREGA; Development Practice; Impact Assessment; Assam etc.

INTRODUCTION:

In India, the policy of creating guaranteed employment through public works dates back to the 1970s when Maharashtra government introduced EGS (Employment Guarantee Scheme). In line with Maharashtra EGS, the government of India introduced the Food for Work Programme for the nation in 1977. In 1980, Food for Work Programme was restructured and renamed as the National Rural Employment Programme (NREP). Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme (RLEGP) was the next in row launched on August 15, 1983. In 1989, NREP and RLEGP were merged together and Jawahar Rojgar Yojana (JRY) was launched. In 1993, the Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS) was launched. In 1999, yet another rural development programme- Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yajana (JGSY) was launched. The National Food for Work Programme (NFWP) was the next in line launched in 2004 targeting 150 backward districts. These programmes had their successes, deficiencies and challenges as well. India underwent fundamental reforms in its economy in the year 1991. Consequent to such reforms, a fall in job creation particularly the unskilled type was visible in the economy. It is against this backdrop, the 'entitlement approach' to public services and public jobs gained legitimacy.

As a result, in 2005 the most refined legislation for poverty eradication and rural development- National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) was passed in the parliament. Same was renamed as Mahatma Gandhi NREGA (MGNREGA) in 2009. By

providing employment the program aimed to put households in a better position to keep up a basic income flow for all. It also aimed at creation of tangible assets to generate 'economies of scale' and thus add income through a multiplier process, besides catering to other social and ecological goals. Never has been in the history of India that any other act received such a wide attention in such a short period of time. The Act has been implemented in phased manner. Altogether, at present it covers 696 districts out of 739 districts of India.

This article, based on a field survey that was carried on in the state of Assam (the largest economy of the North Eastern part of India) in the year 2021-2022, makes a evaluation of this 'Development Practice' based on one important indicators of development i.e. creation of income and employment.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND OBJECTIVES:

Literature on MGNREGA implementation and it's impact on economic, social and other important aspects relevant to our study are briefly reviewed under the following headings-

MGNREGA and Employment

Research undertaken and explanations provided by the scholars and institutions like MoRD, GoI (Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India) 2019, 2014; Panda et.al 2018; World Bank Report 2015; MoRD, GoI 2016, 2008; Kajale and Shroff 2011; Sharma 2010; Hazarika 2009; Murugavel 2009; Drèze 2007; etc. found mostly positive impact of MGNREGA on employment. Though regional variation exists but on the whole for the country MGNREGA has created significant amount of unskilled employment.

Report to the people on MGNREGA, 2005 published by the MoRD, GoI (2016) explained that MGNREGA provide employment to about 5 crore households on an average every year in the country. Report tabled in the state Assembly (Assam) on MGNREGA for FY2011-12, 2012-13 and 2013-14 explained that in 2011-12 total mandays stood at 3.53 crore, while the government could generate 3.14 crore and 2.99 crore mandays in 2012-13 and 2013-14 fiscals respectively (MoRD, GoI 2014). Kajale and Shroff (2011) make an interesting reverse assessment of MGNREGA. They collected primary data from five districts of Maharashtra and found that the state has not been able to show satisfactory performance in terms of employment generation.

MGNREGA and Income:

A number of studies undertaken bring out the positive impact of MGNREGA on the expansion of income of households and individuals. It is also true that there are some studies which question the mechanism of income generation through MGNREGA. The MGNREGA impact on income is explained by the scholars and institutions like McCord and Hannah 2019; Panda 2015; World Bank Report 2015; Sambodhi Research and Communication 2013; Azam 2011; Morgan 2011; Dey and Bedi 2010; Hazarika 2009; Hirway et. al 2009; Shah 2007 etc.

Report on MGNREGA innovations prepared by Anna McCord and Meekha Hannah (2019) explained a number of research findings. It stated that MGNREGA implementation has driven up the rural wages. It has created a wage floor for rural casual labourers by guaranteeing mass employment at a wage which is higher than the market wage for casual agricultural labour.

Researchers identified an overall 4.5% increase in rural casual labour wages during the lean season in districts where the programme was first implemented (Imbert and Papp, 2015). Again the wage floor effect is particularly marked for female labourers with an increase of 8% in MGNREGA districts compared to non-MGNREGA districts. Similarly, using nationally representative National Sample Survey (NSS) data and Difference-in-Difference technique Azam (2011) finds that the impact of NREGA on wages of casual male workers has only been marginal (about 1%).

Study conducted by Sambodhi Research and Communication (2013) on MGNREGA assets creation covering 2381 beneficiaries in 6 selected states found that MGNREGA assets contributed extra income for rural households. Per household income from agriculture and allied activities increased by 15% from Rs.52,600 to Rs.60,600 after the creation of MGNREGA assets. However the study also recorded that a good proportion of households also stopped working under MGNREGA due to additional income generated from MGNREGA created assets.

Above elaboration on MGNREGA implementation and its different impacts explained in review of literature section raise the research questions like what has been the ground level impact of MGNREGA or whether this programme has really brought in some positive impact in context of Assam and North East India. Hence we felt the necessity of undertaking an immediate impact assessment study on the scheme in the state of Assam. Specific objective of this research study is to assess the impact of MGNREGA on income and employment generation. Hypotheses have been formulated to test and verify in the course of the study is MGNREGA has increased the income of rural people.

STATE ASSAM AND SOME MACRO ACHIEVEMENTS OF MGNREGA:

Assam is the largest state in the North East in terms of Population and size of its economy. Its geographical boundary covers an area of 78,438 square kilometers with a population of 3.12 Crores (2011 Population Census). Assam shares 2.43 and 2.58 percentage of land area and population respectively with the country as a whole. Assam is underdeveloped in many of the dimensions of development when compared with the country as a whole. Its literacy rate, gross enrollment ratio are less than the country's average. HDI rank for Assam is below the national average. Unemployment rate in Assam is higher than the country's average. In absence of adequate economic growth (economic growth throughout the 1990s in per capita term was negative) high magnitude of unemployment and poverty is nothing but a colossal social and economic waste. The economy of Assam is largely rural and agrarian in nature. In terms of employment and livelihood, agriculture is still the principal occupation of majority of the rural population in the state.

Initially MGNREGA covered seven districts of Assam in the first phase (2nd February, 2006) and then with the country as a whole it was extended to six more districts in the 2nd phase (1st April, 2007). In the 3rd phase (1st April, 2008) MGNREGA covered all the districts of the state. Implementation time line of MGNREGA in India as well as the state of Assam is explained with the help of the following Table-1.

Table-1: MGNREGA Implementation Time line		
MGNREGA was notified in the country on 7 th September, 2005		
1 st phase: 2 nd February, 2006	Implemented in 200 districts of the country	Included 07 districts of Assam
2 nd phase: 1 st April, 2007	Implemented in 113 districts of the country & extended to 17 more districts of UP (with effect from 15th May, 2007). Altogether included 130 districts.	Included 06 districts of Assam
3 rd phase: 1 st April, 2008	Universalized to include all the districts of India excepts the districts with 100% urban population	Included all the remaining districts of Assam
Included 29 states and 05 union territories of the country (as on May, 2020)		
Included 696 districts out of 739 districts of the country (as on May, 2020)		
Included all the 32 districts of Assam (as on May, 2020)		
Included 7,077 blocks and 269,014 gram panchayats of India (as on May, 2020)		
From 2 nd October, 2009 NREGA is renamed as MGNREGA		

Source: Compiled from MGNREGA site, MoRD, GoI

Presently MGNREGA is the largest Public Employment Programme in the world which employed 52 million rural people and created 2.34 billion person-days of work in 2017-18. As on 2018 total 128.5 million rural households are registered under the scheme, and are eligible for work on demand (30.85% of India's rural population). It is also the largest funded rural development programme in India with an annual budget of USD 8.44 billion in 2019-20 compared to an initial budget of 1.6 billion in 2006-07 (McCord and Paul, 2019). Total expenditure in 2016-17 was 58526.75 crore on 168.74 lakhs of total works (completed work was 66.34 lakh and on-going work was 102.4 lakh) in India. Expenditure on wages was 40793.63 crore while the rest was for material cost. More importantly, 65.88 percent expenditure has been on agricultural and agriculture allied works in 2016-17 which increased from 48 percent in 2013-14 (MGNREGA site, GoI, 2018).

As on June, 2020 total 52.75 Lakh job cards have been issued and total 45.13 Lakh active workers are there under MGNREGA in the state of Assam. Total number of households worked under MGNREGA in the state is 17.42 Lakhs in FY2018-19 and 19.32 Lakhs in FY2019-20. Average days of employment provided per household in Assam were 70 in FY2006-07 and it has come down to 33 in FY2015-16 and 32.32 in FY2019-20. Total number of households which completed 100 days of wage employment in the state during FY2018-19 and FY2019-20 are 18,360 and 30,080 respectively. As on FY2006-07 MGNREGA provided 553.74 Lakhs person days of employment but it has gradually decreased and settled at 532.84 Lakh in FY2018-19. Out of 624.27 Lakh person days of employment generated during FY2019-20 included 4.72% for SCs, 17.6% for STs and 41.77% for women in the state. In FY2019-20 Assam could complete 76,580 nos. of works and similarly 1,42,576 nos. of works in FY2018-19. In FY2019-20, 2.39 lakhs works are ongoing in the state. The act has been providing wage Rs.189 per day per unskilled labour in Assam (as on 2018-19). Total expenditure under MGNREGS in the state of Assam is Rs.1,53,076.32 Lakhs in FY2017-18, Rs.1,33,844.52 Lakhs in FY2018-19 and Rs.1,48,815.38 Lakhs in FY2019-20 (Ministry of Rural Development, Govt. of India).

DATA SOURCE, SAMPLE SELECTION AND METHODS OF ANALYSIS:

We use mainly primary data for the analysis part of the study. Primary data are collected from 'working with MGNREGA' and 'non working with MGNREGA' households of Assam during 2015-16. Unit selection both for MGNREGA workers or treatment or experimental group (EG) and non MGNREGA workers or control group (CG) are based on same sampling stratification and matching covariates. Primary data are collected from Lakhimpur, Morigaon and Nalbari districts of Assam. From the selected 03 sample districts purposively 06 blocks (02 from each district) are chosen. From each block 01 GP (Gram Panchyat) is selected randomly. Finally, 35 MGNREGA working and 35 non MGNREGA working i.e. total 70 households from each village are selected by adopting the method of simple random sampling and looking into the similarity in socio-economic conditions. From each 35 MGNREGA working households 35 workers (EG) 'who worked maximum number of days under MGNREGA' are taken into consideration. From each 35 non MGNREGA working households another 35 non MGNREGA workers (CG, on the basis of main worker criterion of their respective families) are chosen. Unit selection both for EG and CG are based on same sampling stratification and matching covariates.

In terms of tools of economic analysis we used PSM (Propensity Score Matching) and DinD (Difference in Difference). PSM and DinD are applied for gauging the potency of MGNREGS intervention on income, employment, social capital formation and distress migration in the treated (EG) vis-à-vis the non-treated (CG) sample units. Individuals from the treated and non-treated groups having the same PS (Propensity Score) form the matched sample. They share identical features on the covariates. Outcomes of the matched sample are then compared through DinD for inference on the impact of MGNREGS. Covariates applicable for the study are age, educational qualification, marital status and family type. Covariates formed the profile of the clients. It provides a base for a valid and reliable estimation of 'Z'. Comparing all the matched EG and CG sample units paper studied the impacts of MGNREGA over the variables by using statistical computer package i.e. SPSS.

Besides PSM, DinD and general economic understandings derived through Interviews and FGDs (Focus Group Discussion), paper used statistical tests to study the impacts individually on the variables. To assess the impacts of MGNREGA on income and employment we used 'Paired t-test'. Relationship between or among the dependent and independent variables are established by Regression and Correlation studies. Moreover to prove or disprove the stated hypotheses, statistical tables, graphs and other simple statistical tools like ratios, percentages, and different measures of central tendency are used in the study.

In the study both the sample units (EG and CG) are belonging to similar economic strata. Clients considered for PSM are EG 'who have registered and worked maximum number of days during the current year' and CG 'who have registered but not worked in MGNREGA during the current year'. Pre and Post-intervention data are compiled for all the matching sample units of EG and CG. Pre-intervention data are nothing but the annual data for the immediate pre joining period and Post-intervention data are the annual data for the current post joining period for the EG. For the CG, pre and post intervention data are taken for the same annual period as it is for the EG.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS:

Taking four covariates (Age, educational qualification, marital status and family type) DinD is used through PSM to find the total impact of MGNREGA on the variables of the study. Tables and Equations generated through SPSS and PSM data sheets are briefly explained bellow. All the collected 420 sample units are taken into consideration for the study. Logit model is adopted, where Y (regressand) is equal to 1 or 0, '1' signifies the samples from the EG and '0' samples from the CG. Again, X (regressor) indicate the covariates, where X_1 is age, X_2 is educational qualification, X_3 is marital status and X_4 is family type. These covariates form the profile of all the clients. It provides a base for a valid and reliable estimation of 'Z'. Thus, $Y = f(x)$ provides running a logistic regression for $n = 420$ ($1 = 210, 0 = 210$) samples.

Covariates and respective values are given in the following Table-2. Levels of significance are depicted using the Wald test and it formed an integral part of the model.

Table-2: Covariates in the Equation						
	B	S.E.	Wald	df.	Sig.	Exp(B)
Age	0.160	0.084	3.624	1	0.057	1.173
Education	-0.058	0.091	0.408	1	0.523	0.943
Marital status	-0.128	0.110	1.361	1	0.243	0.880
Family type	-0.491	0.210	5.461	1	0.019	0.612
Constant	0.633	0.487	1.689	1	0.194	1.883
Variable(s) entered on step 1: Age, Education, Marital status and Family type						

Source: Authors' SPSS work sheet

Subsequently, the values of 'Z' is derived for all the '420' samples, where-

$$Z = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4$$

Thus, the estimated regression line is-

$$Z = 0.633 + 0.160X_1 - 0.058X_2 - 0.128X_3 - 0.491X_4$$

Total 420 'Z' values are estimated for all the samples of EG and CG. The range of 'Z' derived from the covariates under consideration is (-) 0.933 to 1.222 in the EG and (-) 0.011 to 1.327 in CG. Subsequently, PS is derived through the 'logistic function' of 'Z' by the relation inverse Logit. Further, the Ln (log natural) (PS/1-PS) equals 'Z' (Logit). The score range is 0.2823 to 0.7723 for the EG and 0.3064 to 0.7748 for the CG. Thus, PS are extracted for the 420 samples from the EG and CG.

Samples from the EG and CG having the same PS are balanced on the covariates. They are identical on their profile based on the variables which are taken as covariates and hence some found matched. On matching, 159 matched samples are found spread over 33 different scores. Notably, 06 scores in the EG and 06 scores in the CG are outliers. They fall outside the matching range. Complete result of PSM exercise is explained in the following Table-3.

Variable	Comments	EG (out of 159 samples)		CG (out of 159 samples)		Remark	Ultimate Remark
		No.	%	No.	%		
		Income generation	Increased	93	58		
Not increased	66		42	74	47	EG < CG	
Days of employment	Increased	106	67	73	46	EG > CG	Increased for EG
	Not increased	26	16	61	38	EG < CG	
	Same as before	26	16	25	16	EG = CG	
	Not comparable	01	00	00	00	EG = CG	

Source: Authors' PSM work sheet

Increasing the days of employment and income generation activities, MGNREGS has improved social networking and bindings for the EG units of our study area in Assam. Though differences in acceptance level are seen but the overall impact of MGNREGA in EG unit is found positive for all the four variables of the study.

Now, impact of MGNREGA individually on income and employment variables of the study are analyzed under the following headings-

A. Impact on Income

To understand the impact of MGNREGS on net income we used DiD (double difference) over time for pre and post MGNREGS income. To make the comparison and programme effect more clear non MGNREGA workers or comparison group in addition to the MGNREGA workers or Experimental/Treatment group are taken into consideration. Required data are collected from annual income levels before and after the implementation of the programme both for the comparison and treatment groups. Following Table-4 depicts pre and post MGNREGA income differences for beneficiaries (treatment group).

	Post MGNREGS	Pre MGNREGS	Difference
N	210	210	00
Mean	25096.79	14417.34	10679.45
Minimum	16325.0	12168.0	4157.00
Maximum	27587.0	16543.0	11044.00

Source: Primary survey

Similarly for the non beneficiaries (comparison group) pre and post MGNREGA income differences are stated below in Table-5.

	Post MGNREGS	Pre MGNREGS	Difference
N	210	210	00
Mean	23335.92	15365.50	7970.42
Minimum	15765.0	13870.0	1895.00
Maximum	29900.0	18200.0	11700.00

Source: Primary survey

Now, taking data from the above income differences following equations are created. In equations 'c' is for comparison (non treated) group and 't' for treatment group. Similarly, '0' is for base year and '1' for current year. Equation-1 is created for comparison group and 2 for treatment group. Final equation (equation 3) calculates the net income impact of MGNREGS over the beneficiaries (treatment group).

- a. Income difference before-after for the comparison group (c):

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{y}_{c1} - \bar{y}_{c0} &= \frac{1}{N_c} \sum (y_{j1} - y_{j0}) \text{---(1)} \\ &= 23335.92 - 15365.50 \\ &= 7970.42\end{aligned}$$

The above equation-1 represents the change in income levels for the comparison group due to natural trend and all other events.

- b. Income difference before-after for the treatment group (t):

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{y}_{t1} - \bar{y}_{t0} &= \frac{1}{N_t} \sum (y_{j1} - y_{j0}) \text{---(2)} \\ &= 25096.79 - 14417.34 \\ &= 10679.45\end{aligned}$$

The equation-2 represents the change in income outcomes due to natural trend, all other events and the program effect. Now-

- c. The impact of the program can be found out by:

$$\begin{aligned}impact &= (\bar{y}_{T1} - \bar{y}_{T0}) - (\bar{y}_{C1} - \bar{y}_{C0}) \text{---(3)} \\ &= 10679.45 - 7970.42 \\ &= 2709.03\end{aligned}$$

Thus, DinD for average real income is Rs.2709.03, which is net positive income impact of MGNREGS over the time period. Moreover, results of our exercise undertaken through simple DinD method (equation-3) is further refined by adopting PSM and the results are given bellow in Table-6.

Table-6: Income DinD by PSM	
Total matching sample unit in EG	159
Total matching sample unit in CG	159
PSM score-range for EG	0.2823 to 0.7723
PSM score-range for CG	0.3064 to 0.7748
Sum of income in EG	3987330
Average income of EG	25077.547
Sum of income in CG	3719370
Average income of CG	23392.264
Differences in Sum of Income between EG and CG	267960
Differences in Average Income between EG and CG	1685.28
DinD	1685.28

Source: Authors' PSM work sheet

The DinD of income after matching by PSM is –

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{DinD} &= \text{AverageIncome}_{EG} - \text{AverageIncome}_{CG} \\
 &= 25077.547 - 23392.264 \\
 &= 1685.28 \text{-----} (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

There is positive income impact of MGNREGS. Net annual income difference for working group of population is Rs.1685. Experimental group of population (MGNREGA workers) are earning more than the control group of population (non MGNREGA workers). Thus, both pre and post income DinD (equation-3) and current year income DinD (equation-4 by using PSM) for the beneficiaries are found positive. Therefore, net income impact of MGNREGA is positive.

Further, making various income categories we analyzed the comparative income level of MGNREGA workers before and after the implementation of the Act for all the studied areas. Based on recall method beneficiaries explained their income levels before and after the implementation of MGNREGA. MGNREGA workers from low income category before-MGNREGS have shifted to high income category after-MGNREGS. Income rising trend is depicted in the following Figure-1.

Figure-1: Income Rising Trend Before & After the Implementation (in % of respondents)

Not only income creation, MGNREGS is also a part of disciplinary income generation. To make the act a special one and mitigate the loopholes of corruption, workers' remuneration is paid directly to their bank or post office accounts. It indicates a further step for inclusive growth through MGNREGA. Some of the workers started to keep certain amount of their wage income in bank or post office accounts for long to earn more income in the form of interest and use in time of crises. We observed the situation and income-satisfaction level of MGNREGA workers are found improved over the period.

- ✓ From the analysis (through DinD with and without PSM, table and graphs) it is clear that MGNREGA has positively impacted the income generation in the rural society of our study area. This vindicates the hypothesis that MGNREGA has increased the income base of rural people in the state of Assam.

B. Impact on Employment

Besides PSM (explained in Table-3) Paired-t test is used to evaluate the impact of MGNREGA on employment aspects. We collected information regarding the days of employment before and after the implementation of MGNREGS from the programme beneficiaries (EG) of Assam. Following Table-7 explained paired sample statistics for N=210 beneficiaries. Post MGNREGS mean annual employment days are more than the pre MGNREGS mean annual employment days for the beneficiaries of Assam.

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Post MGNREGS annual employment for beneficiaries	76.5810	210	10.60178	0.73159
Pre MGNREGS annual employment for beneficiaries	62.3952	210	11.22842	0.77483

Source: Authors' SPSS work sheet

Paired sample correlation both for pre and post MGNREGS employment is given in following Table-8. Correlation obtained +0.688 depicts high positive correlation between pre and post MGNREGS days of employment.

Post MGNREGS & Pre MGNREGS annual employment for beneficiaries in Assam	N	Correlation	Sig.
	210	0.688	0.000

Source: Authors' SPSS work sheet

Results for the paired sample test are given in the following Table-9. Since $P \leq 0.05$, at 5% level of significance we may reject the null hypothesis. Hence there are significant difference in the pre and post annual days of employment for the programme beneficiaries in Assam. The mean difference is positive. Impact of MGNREGS on employment is found positive.

Post and Pre MGNREGS annual employment for the beneficiaries	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
	1.41857E1	8.64443	0.59652	13.00974	15.36169	23.781	209	0.000

Source: Authors' SPSS work sheet

Moreover, more than 80% sample beneficiaries mentioned about the increasing trend of employment opportunities during the days of MGNREGS. Scenario is stated in the following Table-10.

District	Village	Increased		Decreased		Remained Same	
		Nos.	%	Nos.	%	Nos.	%
Nalbari	Barbukiya	33	94.29	01	2.86	01	2.86
	Sungarbori	30	85.71	01	2.86	04	11.43
<i>Total (% with district total sample respondent)</i>		<i>63</i>	<i>90.00</i>	<i>02</i>	<i>2.86</i>	<i>05</i>	<i>7.14</i>
Morigaon	Khanajan	34	97.14	00	00	01	2.86
	Baghara	30	85.71	01	2.86	04	11.43
<i>Total (% with district total sample respondent)</i>		<i>64</i>	<i>91.43</i>	<i>01</i>	<i>1.43</i>	<i>05</i>	<i>7.14</i>
Lakhimpur	Jalbhari	29	82.86	02	5.71	04	11.43
	No. 2 Dimar.	31	88.57	00	00	04	11.43
<i>Total (% with district total sample respondent)</i>		<i>60</i>	<i>85.71</i>	<i>02</i>	<i>2.86</i>	<i>08</i>	<i>11.43</i>
<i>Grand total (% with state total sample respondent)</i>		<i>187</i>	<i>89.05</i>	<i>05</i>	<i>2.38</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>8.57</i>

Source: Primary survey

As explained in the above table, minimum 60% programme beneficiaries of Assam also mentioned about the increasing trend of days of employment.

- ✓ From the analysis (done through PSM and Paired-t test) it is evident that MGNREGA has positively impacted the wage employment creation in our study area. This vindicates the hypothesis that MGNREGA has led to increase in rural wage employment in the state of Assam.

Thus, using PSM, DiD and Paired test tools study finds that MGNREGA intervention has increased the income level of the EG vis.-a-vis. the CG. This increase in income has been found statistically significant. Using the same tools, positive impact of MGNREGA on wage-employment creation is detected.

CONCLUSION:

Presently the state of Assam is embedded with a lot of deficiencies in many dimensions of economic development. With a high poverty ratio and unemployment rate, the state is finding it difficult to catch up with the rest of India. Three decades of uncertainty and confusion from 1970s to the end of 1990s, has put the whole economy of Assam in the Libenstian's framework of low equilibrium trap. Post 2000, when economic growth has started unfolding, challenges to economic development particularly in the rural sector also manifest openly and intensely. It is against this backdrop, implantation of MGNREGA was extremely relevant and timely in the state of Assam. Our finding that MGNREGA has been instrumental in increasing the income and employment base of the rural economy reinforces the faith in a development practice like MGNREGA and it's cardinal features.

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